

RESULTS OF TREATMENT OF CHRONIC RECURRENT HERPETIC STOMATITIS

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Chronic recurrent herpetic stomatitis (CRHS) is one of the most common pathologies and accounts for 85% of the total number of patients with diseases of the oral mucosa who applied to the dental clinic. The dental status of patients with chronic recurrent herpetic stomatitis of the oral mucosa and red border is characterized by multiple elements of the lesion (stain, vesicle, bladder, erosion, crust) and pathological processes (spongiosis, acantholysis, ballooning dystrophy, vacuolar dystrophy), bleeding and inflammation of the gums.

Purpose of the study. To increase and evaluate the effectiveness of the treatment of herpes simplex by including the drug "Kagocel" in the complex of etiopathogenetic therapeutic measures.

Material and research methods. The study included 35 patients (12 men and 23 women) with chronic recurrent herpetic stomatitis aged 18 to 50 years. All patients were examined and treated at the Department of Therapeutic Dentistry of the Bukhara State Medical Institute. In all patients, the frequency of exacerbation of CRHS was more than 3 times a year, the duration of the disease was more than one year. The study included patients in the phase of exacerbation of the process, but not more than 48 hours after the onset of rashes. All patients (35 people) received the antiviral drug interferon inducer "Kagocel" 2 tablets (12 mg) 3 times a day for 5 days. To implement the tasks set, a unified scheme for examining patients with chronic recurrent herpetic stomatitis was developed.

Research results and discussion. As a result of the study, 71,4% of women and 28,6% of men had herpetic gingivostomatitis. Herpes simplex lip was observed in 34,5% of men and 65,5% of women, respectively. Antiviral therapy with the Kagocel interferon inducer does not cause allergic reactions and side effects, makes it possible to continue therapy in the remission phase and is clinically effective (reduces the epithelialization period and increases the remission period). The influence of herpes virus infection on the state of local immunity of the oral cavity has been confirmed, which is explained not only by immunosuppression, but also by an increase in oral tolerance. The most pronounced activation of humoral immunity in the oral fluid has been proven.

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